

Century of notable research in chemistry^Ψ

M. Verma, G. Seshadri and R. K. Khandal

Shriram Institute for Industrial Research, 19, University Road, Delhi-110 007, India

E-mail : sridhi@vsnl.com

Fax : 91-11-27667676, 27667207

Manuscript received 6 June 2005

Ever since life originated on earth, several evolutionary phenomena have been taking place naturally as well as by virtue of the growth of living organisms. One of the most significant evolutionary happening has been the advent of the human race. The process must have taken ages but once the human race came into existence, there have been fast changes (developments!) all around. The basic instinct of mankind to explore newer vistas and ways for livelihood as well as for comforts can be ascribed to the inquisitiveness to know more about things. The use of available resources for personal benefits have, infact, caused a lot of burden to the environment and ecology. Awareness (knowledge) about things around us is one distinct trait that the humans are blessed with. With time, there have been continuous improvements in the knowledge. While the exploitation of resources using the knowledge base created by mankind could be blamed for the environment-related problems, it is the same knowledge base which will help us to find solutions for many problems around.

The scientific developments have been responsible for various activities, events and happenings around us. Starting from the stone age to the present electronic age, the journey has not been very smooth and straight forward. The zeal to communicate, make communities and acquire things including the manpower and animal power has been the driving force for all that mankind has passed through. There were ups and downs, because of the right and wrong use of the scientific developments respectively. When we look back in the history, the following major issues emerge as the key to many inventions and discoveries with time.

The above mentioned details are only an oversimplification of the scientific research undertaken across the continents by scientists and technologists from multidisciplinary areas of expertise over the century. Since

Table 1. Issues responsible for inventions and discoveries

Issues	Essential components	Inventions/ discoveries
(a) Livelihood, Survival	Food, Water, Fire, Colonies	Agriculture Animal husbandry Housing
(b) Domination, Authority, rule	Arms Ammunition	Explosives Weapons, Nuclear devices
(c) Communication	Devices for conveying messages; oral as well as written	Telegraph, Telephone, Electronics
(d) Movement, Gypsy nature	Transport devices to carry live stock and other materials from place to place; in time and with ease	Transport systems : Surface Water Air
(e) Growth, sustainability	Support systems and auxiliaries	Materials, Fuels

the results of each study triggered the scope for several other related or unrelated studies, the whole process of scientific developments seen at macro level would present a very well coordinated as also integrated efforts by multidisciplinary groups of scientists at micro level. Therefore, no one field can claim to be the sole contributor to the developments seen around us today. However, one can always list and elaborate the notable developments (in a given area) that became the source of further research for other areas. This is what has been attempted in this chapter which basically deals with the notable research in chemistry during the last century.

A century is not a very big time period when one takes into account the total historical period of human race. It is not a very large period also because of the fact that the human body is designed to last almost for a cen-

^ΨDedicated to Professor H. C. Gaur on his 80th birthday.

ture. Hence, anything that has occurred during this time period can easily be envisaged and appreciated by the present generation. This attempt becomes relevant especially because of the reason that it is being dedicated to the 80th anniversary of Prof. Gaur who has not only been witness to most of the developments in this century but has also contributed a great deal by his own research. Moreover, the difference in the situations at the beginning of the two centuries i.e. 20th and the 21st is so vast that it is worth looking at the researches during this period. Here, only the developments related to chemistry are discussed.

Nobel Prizes in Chemistry

To recognize and promote the innovative research in all streams including chemistry, physics, medicine, literature, history and economics the great achievers are honored with the Nobel prize each year since 1901 for their unique contribution to the society. Nobel prizes are given in the memory of Sir Alfred Nobel, inventor of

dynamite and a great chemist of his time. Sir Nobel who died in 1896 had desired in his will that Nobel prizes be awarded each year from 1901 (beginning of 20th century!) onwards. Let us view the notable research in chemistry from the standpoint of nobel prizes awarded so far.

The Tables 2a-h present the details of the Nobel prizes awarded during the last century in various disciplines of chemistry.

While discoveries about noble gases, fluorine and Haber process led to a vast range of chemistries for diversified applications, the molecular orbital theory, organometallics and complexes helped in the overall understanding of complex compounds. A complete range of inorganic compounds for numerous purposes became possible by virtue of the contributions listed in Table 2a as well as the other studies done in this area. Here, it may be noted that in the last two decades, there has been no Nobel prize in this discipline.

Discoveries of radioactive substances, and fission reactions are the notable discoveries in nuclear chemistry

Table 2a. Nobel Prizes in Inorganic Chemistry

Year	Scientists	Discovery/contribution
1904	W. Ramsay	Inert gases
1906	H. Moissan	Fluorine and its applications
1913	A. Werner	Linkage of atoms in molecules
1914	T. W. Richards	Atomic weight determination
1918	F. Haber	Synthesis of ammonia
1922	F. W. Aston	Whole number rule
1936	P. J. W. Debye	Structure by dipole moment and XRD
1954	L. C. Pauling	Chemical bonding
1966	R. S. Mulliken	Molecular orbital theory
1973	E. O. Fischer; Sir G. Wilkinson	Sandwich compounds
1976	W. N. Liscomb	Structure of boranes
1983	H. Taube	Electron transfer reaction in metal complexes

Table 2b. Nobel Prizes in Nuclear Chemistry

Year	Scientists	Discovery/contribution
1908	L. E. Rutherford	Disintegration of the elements
1911	M. Curie	Radium and polonium
1921	F. Soddy	Isotopes
1934	H. C. Urey	Heavy hydrogen
1935	F. Joliot; I. J. Curie	Synthesis of new radioactive elements
1943	G. De Hevesy	Use of isotopes as tracer
1944	O. Hahn	Fission of heavy nuclei
1951	E. M. McMillan; G. T. Seaborg	Transuranic elements
1960	W. F. Libby	C-14 applications

which led to the construction of atom bomb as well as the utilization of nuclear energy for peaceful purposes. Starting from the beginning of the 20th century, the scientists devoted most of their time in understanding matter but after the atom bomb attack on Hiroshima and Nagasaki, there have been only four Nobel prizes in nuclear chemistry and that too only because of the use of nuclear chemistry for peaceful purposes. No Nobel prize in nuclear chemistry has been awarded in last forty five years as shown in Table 2b.

Discovery of fullerenes, Grignard reagent, organic dyes, boron, phosphorous, sulphur and halo compounds besides the art of organic synthesis led to an innumerable range of organic compounds being used in almost all spheres of our lives. The knowledge to predetermine the course of chemical reactions and design products with desired applications has added new dimensions to industrial chemical processes. Synthesis and reaction mechanism is one discipline of chemistry which still draws the attention of researchers as is evident from the four Nobel prizes awarded during the last decade of the 20th century.

Discoveries of haemin, insulin, alkaloids, amino acid

sequencing of nucleic acids, globular proteins have been the highlights which has helped both the drug and pharmaceutical industries to a great extent. Biochemistry appear to be the discipline of chemistry for the 21st century as is also evident from the fact that the last three prizes were awarded to studies in this area. Moreover, in times to come, efforts would be to develop alternate routes (preferably bio routes) to derive products for various applications.

Invention of X-ray diffraction, polarographic methods and NMR spectroscopy in the 20th century are the important discoveries in analytical chemistry as indicated by Table 2e, which has helped the structural elucidation of various simple and complex organic molecules. Infact, most of the chemistries could be known only because of the developments in analytical chemistry; a most essential tool not only to know about the chemical constitution but also for tailor making any given product.

The single discovery of Ziegler-Natta catalyst in the 20th century marked a revolutionary phase as far as material science is concerned as evident from Table 2f. Today, polymers have acquired the prime place in almost everything that we use for our daily life. Nobel Prize of

Table 2c. Nobel Prizes in Organic Chemistry (Synthesis and Reaction Mechanism)

Year	Scientists	Discovery/contribution
1905	J. F. W. Adolf Von Baeyer	Organic dyes and hydroaromatics
1910	O. Wallach	Alicyclic compounds
1912	V. Grignard; P. Sabatier	Grignard reagent
1950	O. P. H. Diels; K. Alder	Diene synthesis
1956	Sir C. N. Hinshelwood; N. N. Semenov	Mechanism of chemical reaction
1965	R. B. Woodward	Art of organic synthesis
1969	Sir D. H. R. Barton; O. Hassel	Concept of conformation and its application
1971	G. Herzberg	Geometry and structure of free radicals
1975	Sir J. W. Cornforth; V. Prelog	Stereochemistry of organic reactions
1979	H. C. Brown; G. Wittig	Use of boron and phosphorous compounds
1981	K. Fukui; R. Hoffmann	Course of chemical reactions
1984	R. B. Merrifield	Chemical synthesis on solid matrix
1986	D. R. Herschbach; Y. T. Lee; J. C. Polanyi	Dynamics of chemical elementary processes
1987	D. J. Cram; J. M. Lehn; C. J. Pedersen	Highly selective molecules
1990	E. J. Corey	Theory of organic synthesis
1994	G. A. Olah	Carbocation chemistry
1996	R. F. Curl (Jr); R. E. Smalley; Sir H. W Kroto	Fullerenes
1999	A. Zewail	Transition state of chemical reactions
2001	W. S. Knowles; R. Noyori; K. B. Sharpless	Chirally catalysed oxidation and hydrogenation reactions

Table 2d. Nobel Prizes in Biochemistry

Year	Scientists	Discovery/contribution
1902	H. E. Fischer	Sugar and purine synthesis
1907	E. Buchner	Cell free fermentation
1915	R. M. Willstätter	Chlorophyll
1927	H. O. Wieland	Constitution of bile acids
1928	A. O. R. Windaus	Constitution of sterol
1929	Sir A. Harden; H. K. A. S. Yon Euler-Chelpin	Fermentation of sugar
1930	H. Fischer	Synthesis of haemin
1937	Sir W. N. Haworth; P. Karrer	Carbohydrates and vitamins
1938	R. Kuhn	Carotenoids and vitamins
1939	A. F. J. Butenandt	Sex hormones
1945	A. I. Virtanen	Method of fodder preservation
1946	J. B. Sumner; W. M. Stanley; J. H. Northrop	Studies on enzyme and virus proteins
1947	Sir R. Robinson	Alkaloids
1953	H. Staudinger	Macromolecular chemistry
1955	V. D. Vigneaud	Polypeptide hormone
1957	L. A. R. Todd	Nucleotide and nucleotide co-enzymes
1958	F. Sanger	Structure of insulin
1961	M. Calvin	CO ₂ assimilation in plants
1962	M. F. Perutz; Sir J. C. Kendrew	Structure of globular proteins
1970	L. F. Leloir	Sugar nucleotides and role in biosynthesis
1972	C. B. Anfinsen; S. Moore; W. H. Stein	Amino acid sequence and catalytic activity in RNA
1978	P. D. Mitchell	Chemiosmotic theory
1980	P. Berg; W. Gilbert; F. Sanger	Biochemistry of nucleic acids
1988	J. Deisenhofer; R. Huber; H. Michel	3-D structure of photosynthetic reaction centre
1989	S. Altman; T. R. Cech	Catalytic properties of RNA
1993	K. B. Mullis; M. Smith	Studies on mutagenesis
1997	P. D. Boyer; J. E. Walker; J. C. Skou	Ion transporting enzyme and mechanism of ATP synthesis
2002	J. B. Fenn; K. Tanaka; K. Wuthrich	Studies on biological macromolecules
2003	P. Agre; R. Mackinnon	Water and ion channels in cell membranes
2004	A. Ciechanover; I. Rose; A. Hershko	Ubiquitin – mediated protein degradation

the year 2000 given for discovery of conducting polymers opened up the possibilities of polymers and plastics being used in the electronic industry. The work on development of biodegradable polymers and smart polymers drew the attention of scientists in 21st century.

Table 2g represents the Nobel prizes awarded in the field of physical chemistry. Discovery of various principles related to thermodynamics, thermochemistry, chemical equilibrium and surface chemistry in 20th century provided us with a better understanding of different chemical processes.

A single Nobel prize has been awarded in atmospheric chemistry as evident from Table 2h. The formation and

decomposition of ozone has provided a better understanding of the greenhouse effect.

Major contributions of research in chemistry

Having had a look at the Nobel prizes awarded in various areas of chemistry, it would not be a bad idea if we now list some of the notable consequences of the research in chemistry during the 20th century. This would perhaps, enable us to realize the relevance of each of these prizes as also of the other research contributions which might not have received a Nobel prize but yet has led to notable changes in our life and lifestyle.

Periodic table :

One of the major outcomes of the breakthroughs in

Table 2e. Nobel Prizes in Analytical Chemistry

Year	Scientists	Discovery/contribution
1923	Fritz Pregl	Microanalysis of organic substances
1948	A. W. K. Tiselius	Studies on serum protein
1952	A. J. P. Martin; R. L. M. Synge	Partition chromatography
1959	J. Heyrovsky	Polarographic method of analysis
1964	D. C. Hodgkin	Structure of biochemical substances by XRD
1982	Sir A. Klug	Crystallographic electron microscopy
1985	H. A. Hauptman; J. Karle	Crystal structure determination
1991	R. R. Ernst	NMR spectroscopy
1992	R. A. Marcus	Theory of electron transfer reaction

Table 2f. Noble Prizes in Material Science/Polymer

Year	Scientists	Discovery/contribution
1963	K. Ziegler; G. Natta	Chemistry of high polymers
2000	A. J. Heeger; H. Shirakawa; A. G. MacDiarmid	Conducting polymers

Table 2g. Nobel Prizes in Physical Chemistry

Year	Scientists	Discovery/contribution
1901	J. H. Van't Hoff	Laws of chemical dynamics
1903	S. A. Arrhenius	Electrolytic theory of dissociation
1909	W. Ostwald	Principles for chemical equilibrium
1920	W. H. Nernst	Thermochemistry
1925	R. A. Zsigmondy	Heterogenous nature of colloid solutions
1931	C. Bosch; F. Bergius	Chemical high pressure methods
1932	I. Langmuir	Surface chemistry
1949	W. F. Giauque	Behavior of substance at low temperature
1967	M. Eigen; R. G. W. Norrish; L. G. Porter	Studies on extremely fast chemical reactions
1968	L. Onsager	Reciprocal relations
1974	P. J. Flory	Fundamental of macromolecules
1977	I. Prigogine	Theory of dissipative structures
1998	W. Kohn; J. A. Pople	Computational method in quantum chemistry

Table 2h. Nobel Prizes in Atmospheric Chemistry

Year	Scientists	Discovery/contribution
1995	P. Crutzen; F. S. Rowland; M. Molina	Formation and decomposition of ozone

chemistry was the construction of the periodic table. A necessary prerequisite for the making of the periodic table was the discovery of the individual elements. By 1869 a total of 63 elements had been discovered. As the number of known elements grew, the need to develop classification schemes arose. Though the efforts for construction of the periodic table started in the late 19th century, it was in the 20th century that the periodic table retained its final and if we can say an advanced form with most of its

holes filled with different elements. Dmitri Ivanovich Mandeleev is considered as the father of the periodic table for the pioneer work resulting in the construction of the periodic table. The subsequent developments in periodic table were continued. The major achievements were the discovery of noble gases and transuranic elements by William Ramsay and Glenn Seaborg. The construction of the periodic table has led to a very useful framework for classifying informations and acquiring data related to prop-

erties of elements and their compounds useful not only to chemists but also physicists, spectroscopists and metallurgists.

The periodic table has today become the basic tool which teachers all over the world use while teaching chemistry to the beginners.

Metals and Minerals :

Experimentations and inventions throughout the century in metallurgy, metal production technology and metals forming and shaping resulted in the ability to produce metals of highest purity on the one hand, alloys of higher strength, corrosion resistance and resistance to abrasion and erosion in chemically aggressive and high temperature regimes on the other. Light weight, low density metals, such as aluminium and titanium became important. In steel making, the basic oxygen and electric arc furnaces replaced the Bessemer and open hearth furnaces. Technological improvements in glass making resulted in tougher, stronger and more brilliant glasses, and low thermal expansion borosilicate glass with improved shatter resistance. Innovations in chemical methods improved the technologies for example, the lead chamber batch process for making H_2SO_4 was replaced by high volume contact process with associated electric cogeneration plants. Lead oxide and barium/zinc base lithopone which were used as white pigment in early 20th century were replaced by better choices such as titanium dioxide, which improved whiteness and reduced health hazards from heavy metal ingestion.

The revolution in communication occurred with the discovery of materials required for cables. The devices ranging from nickel and lithium for batteries to germanium and silicon for semiconductors became an integral part of various appliances. With these developments, discoveries of radio, telephone and television could be made possible. Commercial radio broadcasting was established in 1920 and commercial television broadcasting, after World War-II. Both these devices bridged the gap that time difference and distance had created; bringing people, countries and continents together.

Nuclear Chemistry :

Nuclear radiations are high energy radiations whose exposure may result in cell damage leading to fatal chronic conditions. But their use in a controlled manner may bring wonders. The research carried out in nuclear chemistry in the 20th century made a notable contribu-

tion of using radiations for life saving therapies.

The origin of nuclear chemistry occurred with the studies carried out by Sir L. E. Rutherford on the disintegration of the element and the chemistry of the radioactive substances for which he was awarded the Nobel prize in 1908. After this, nuclear fission and fusion methods were investigated. The world soon entered the atomic age in 1942 with the initiation of controllable self sustaining nuclear chain reaction by Enrico Fermi. Unfortunately, the first major exposure of mankind to these discoveries were through the use of destructive weapons such as the Atomic Bomb!

The use of atomic energy for peaceful purposes began after World War-II and wonders were predicted for this new technology. The first small step towards this was taken in 1951 with the setting up of an experimental power reactor for the generation of electricity. The harnessing of nuclear energy for mankind progressed further in various areas. Today, the major portion of electricity produced in France, for example, is from nuclear energy. India is also not behind and has plans to expand its existing sizable capacity of power generation from nuclear energy.

Food irradiation is another wonderful use of nuclear chemistry, which makes the food safer to eat and have a longer shelf life. The food is irradiated in such a way that it restricts the growth of disease caused by micro-organisms without affecting the quality, flavor or texture of the food. This also makes food safer and also keeps it fresh for a longer period. The widely used radioisotope for this purpose is Co-60. Today, this radiation process is most widely used for spices, herbs, dehydrated vegetables, and also meat products such as pork and poultry to improve their shelf life without affecting their quality.

Nuclear chemistry plays an extremely important role in medical sciences; for the diagnosis and treatment of cancer and heart diseases. In addition to this, bone imaging is another application of radioisotopes which has proved wonderful to diagnose arthritis patients, bone fractures and various other bone abnormalities.

Nuclear chemistry also helps in collecting information for archeological dating, in agriculture to understand the chemical and biological processes in plants.

Nuclear radiations are enormously beneficial for mankind if used in a controlled way for applications such as generation of power, diagnostics and curing of various

diseases, inspite of the deadly experience of Hiroshima and Nagasaki in World War-II. As a matter of fact, the use of nuclear radiation is one glaring example of how knowledge can be used for both the destructive as well as constructive purposes. It would be appropriate to say that "It is not the technology but the avarice of man which destroys the Mankind".

Agriculture :

The 20th century brought noticeable developments in the area of agriculture. Presently, the widespread use of the chemicals such as herbicides, pesticides, insecticides and mineral rich fertilizers are responsible not only for quality crop with higher productivity but also for protecting the agricultural products from insects infestations after the harvesting is done. The role of research in chemistry in agricultural developments is quite evident here.

The first widely used herbicide was 2,4-di chlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) during the late 1940s. 2,4-D was known for its poor selectivity and also for less effectiveness against some broad leaf weeds. Later on, Atrazine (1970s) and Glyphosate (1980s) were the popular discoveries but they were again nonselective. Moreover, Atrazine was also found responsible for ground water contamination. All this led to several other innovative products. The pairing of herbicides along with the development of resistant seeds led to the consolidation of the seed technology and pesticide industry in the late 1990s. Modern chemical herbicides of 21st century for agriculture are specifically formulated to decompose within a short period after their application. This is desirable as it allows crops which may be affected by the herbicides to be grown on the land during the following season. Some of the popular herbicides presently used are Paraquat, 2,4-D, Clopyralid, Metolachlor, Dicamba, Picloran etc. Likewise, the use of a range of pesticides, fungicides and insecticides have also contributed a great deal in achieving the target of producing food for all.

The chlorinated aromatic compounds, organophosphates, thio and thiocarbamates and pyrethroids are some of the notable product range made possible by the research in organic synthesis as well as on the structure-activity correlations.

Dairy Chemistry :

If we look back over the past century, dairy science and technology has been one field where chemistry has played an important role. Uptil 20th century, milk was known to contain a milk protein called lactose, triglycer-

ides, lipids and proteins. The subsequent developments in biochemistry for example, (i) elucidation of sequence of proteins; (ii) placement of the disulphide bonds in the whey protein; (iii) three dimensional structure of β -lactoglobulin, α -lactalbumin, immunoglobulins, lactoferrin and serum albumin led to the emergence of dairy industry. The more recent researches on nucleotide technologies enabled the sequencing of the milk protein genes and thus allowed the cloning of a range of mutant proteins.

The innovations of the past few decades helped the mechanization of dairy processing resulting in standardized milk quality with low production price. In the years to come, new chemical technologies and increased globalization will provide the dairy industry with a scope to exploit the potential of dairy science.

Drugs and Pharmaceuticals :

Organic Chemistry has been instrumental for the major advancements in understanding the structure and functions of different molecules including the biomolecules. This has had an enormous impact on developments in the chemicals and petrochemical industry but more importantly on the advances in the biomedical sciences. For instance, in 1954 the first naturally occurring protein hormone (oxytocin) was analysed and synthesized. During this period, for the first time it was shown that an artificially produced protein has exactly the same properties as those that are naturally produced. The synthesis of insulin, a life saving protein for diabetics followed shortly thereafter. In 1959 the 3-d structure of haemoglobin (the oxygen transporting molecules that are responsible for redness of blood) was determined at atomic resolution. Since then, the structure of thousands of biologically important molecules have been described. The knowledge of organic chemistry has played an increasingly important role in the development of novel diagnostics and therapeutics. Today, in the age of fast computers, medicinal chemists are able to use the knowledge of biomolecular structures to design small compounds with very specific plasmacological properties.

Modern biochemistry which is a combination of traditional fields of physiology and pathology with all branches of the chemical sciences, has made crucial contributions both to our understanding about our life processes and to the drugs and pharmaceutical industries in the 20th century. Discovery of antibiotics by Paul Ehrlich was the major break through in this field. Further advancements in the field of antibiotics are attributed to Alexander

Fleming and Selman Waksman for the development of penicillin and streptomycin. Today, a variety of antibiotics have been elucidated to control various bacterial infections. Some of the presently popular antibiotics are Gentamicin, Neomycin, Carbapenems, Cephamycins, Erythromycin, Ciprofloxacin, Levofloxacin, Sulphonamides, Tetracyclin, Chloramphenicol, Clindamycin and Trimethoprim etc. A large range of antibiotics were developed depending upon the specificity or spectrum of microbial infections, only due to the discovery of penicillin and streptomycin. This is one example of how notable research work can lead to a series of products. The other major achievement of the 20th century was the introduction of chemotherapy which virtually grew out of a World War-I study on the toxic effects of mustard gas. Radiography and radiotherapy had stemmed out from early research conducted by Madam Curie and her husband in mid 1900s. This has enabled us to cure and control incurable ailments Today, various radioactive trace elements (e.g. C0-60) are being used to control cancer.

Material Sciences :

The earlier eras were characterized as the ages of stone, iron and copper. The 20th century which can be called as the "age of engineered materials" is mainly due to the developments in material sciences.

The revolution in material sciences started in the 20th century with the developments like heavy building blocks of iron and steel and ended up with the lighter weight metal alloys and exotic high strength composites. Analytical methods coupled with the powerful computational tools have further helped in completely revolutionalising the research in material science.

The introduction of synthetic polymer was the major breakthrough of the 20th century. Polymer materials display properties that are unique when compared to other materials like metal, glass or wood and so have contributed greatly to improve the quality of our everyday life. Polymers have touched each and every field of human life. Clothing, housing, automobiles, aircraft, packaging, electronics, signs, recreation items, and medical implants are some of such examples.

The synthetic polymer industry started in 1909 with the development of phenol formaldehyde resin (Bakelite). Polymer industry really blossomed in the late 1930s with

the discovery of polyethylene, nylon, urethane, fluorocarbon, fiber glass, acrylics and styrene.

Particularly among fluorocarbons, polytetrafluoroethylene popularly known as Teflon was one of the most popular and commercially successful plastics developed in 1930s which could be deposited on metal surfaces as a scratchproof and corrosion resistant, low friction protective coating. By the early 1960s and even today, Teflon "non-stick" frying pans are a favourite consumer items of every kitchen.

In the midst of 20th century polypropylene, polyester (Dacron) and heat resistant super polymers were invented which further revolutionized the polymer industry. It will not be wrong, if we say that such contributions of research in polymer chemistry are today responsible for providing clothing for all in the world.

Polyimides discovered in 1964, also proved to be a very interesting group of polymers as far as properties like heat resistance and chemical resistance are concerned. Their strength and heat resistance is so great that these materials are capable of replacing glass and metals; steel can be replaced by polymeric materials in many demanding industrial applications. Discovery of semiconductors and silicon chips have revolutionized not only the electronics industry but also the telecommunication industry. The invention of desktop computers and laptops have never been complete without the discovery of semiconductors, silicon chips and liquid crystals.

One of the most potentially important new developments in material science is the electronic circuit made out of plastics called conductive polymers such as polyaniline. Electronic circuits fabricated using plastics or other related materials that could be simply printed on the substrate could be incredibly cheap; opening the possibility of cheaper electronic devices.

Discovery of liquid crystal polymers in late 1980s is another class which finds application in high strength fibers and display industry. Kevlar, which is used to make things like helmets, bullet proof vests etc. is just one example of the use of polymeric liquid crystals in applications meant for strong but light weight materials.

Remarkable new biomaterials based on polymers are being continuously to be developed for use in making heart-assist devices, artificial kidneys, contact lenses, vascular grafts, shunts, sutures, prostheses and hundreds of other products.

Origin of Life

Besides carrying out research on the basic disciplines of sciences, the researches in all fields have been found possessed with the aim to know the origin of life. Researches in chemistry have also contributed to this quest. The experiments addressing the fundamental question of the generation of life on earth was performed during the early 1950s to explore the genesis of the first organic compounds out of inorganic ones under the supposed conditions of the earth's surface some 3.5 billion years ago. It was predicted that under the appropriate conditions, organic molecules emerged that could well have been the building blocks of early life. Although many of these results are somewhat hypothetical, it became quite clear that the genesis of life on earth was possible on the basis of physical and chemical principles alone, without the need to invoke supernatural forces. Today, the preferred hypothesis concerning the origin of life on earth holds that life made its first appearance in the form of RNA molecule capable of catalyzing their own synthesis. Therefore, chemical evolution might well have led to the first key molecule of life, furnishing the earth with prerequisites of biological evolution.

The recent developments in cellular and molecular biology along with the concepts of nano-chemistry appear to open up new frontiers in scientific research which will change the course of things completely, in the times to come.

Conclusion :

During the 20th century, and especially over last few decades, scientific research has greatly increased our understanding of the fundamental constitution of matter, the origin of the universe, the evolution of life on earth, the structure and function of biomolecules and much more. At the dawn of the 21st century, science finds itself at an even more challenging situation where many of our natural resources are declining raising enormous questions pertaining to food supply, public health, global climate change, protection of biodiversity and many more.

No doubt, the chemistry or chemical sciences have made breath-taking advances during the past hundred years. They have provided innumerable benefits through an extremely wide range of applications. These include, new materials, food additives, pharmaceuticals and pesticides and also novel analytical tools and techniques for the study of living matter as well as environment.

The 20th century was also bracketed by the scientific and industrial revolutions in many ways. During this period advancement in all the branches of sciences occurred with chemistry at the central theme. Innovative developments in core and applied chemistry and technologies over the next few decades promise to affect virtually all aspects of everyday life, from transportation to healthcare, communication to recreation. Engineers and scientists envision superefficient cars, smart offices with wireless sensors, automobile fuel cells in the decades to come. Use of nanotechnology in the creation of functional materials, devices and systems through control of matter on nanometer scale and exploitation of novel phenomenon and properties will be the thrust areas of this millennium.

While we talk about the advantages that we derived from notable research in chemistry, it will be a job half done if we do not focus on the hazards created by the advances in chemistry during the 20th century. Dealing with the hazardous and toxic substance alongwith the adverse impact of over exploitation of research by virtue of the scientific developments would be the challenges for the future.

Not denying the fact that notable research in chemistry has been responsible for several hazardous substances, it is to be noted that the existing knowledge base can be enough to get rid of these substances besides finding newer and green routes to manufacture alternatives.

References for further reading

1. Chemistry : The Central Science by T. L Brown and H. E. Lemay, 8th ed., Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, NJ, 1999.
2. Chemistry and Chemical Reactivity by J. C. Kotz and P. Treichel, 4th ed., Harcourt, Brace College, Fort Worth Tx, 1999.
3. Chemistry : Molecular Nature of Matter and Change by M. S. Silberberg, McGraw-Hill College, Blacklick, Ohio, USA, 2002.
4. Progress in Pesticide Biochemistry and Toxicology (Progress in Pesticide Biochemistry) by D. H. Hutson and T. R. Roberts, John Wiley & Sons Ltd., 1983.
5. Pesticides in Fruits and Vegetables by S. E. Kegley and L. J. Wise, University Science Books, 1998.
6. Chemistry for Changing Times by J. W. Hill and D. K. Kolb, Prentice Hall Books, Lebanon, Indiana, USA, 1997.
7. Development in Modern Chemistry by A. J. Inde, Dover Publications Inc., Mineola, New York, USA, 1984.
8. The Origin of Life by A. I. Oparin, 2nd ed., Dover Publication, 1953.
9. The Fifth Miracle : the Search for the Origin and Meaning of Life by Paul Davies, Simon & Schuster, 2000.

10. Industrial Dyes by K. Hunger, John Wiley & Sons Ltd., 2002.
11. Natural Dyes, Plants and Processes by Jack Kramer, MacMillan Pub. Co., 1972.
12. Biochemistry by G. Garrett, 2nd ed., Thomas Books/Cole, 1999.
13. Crucibles : the Story of Chemistry from Ancient Alchemy to Nuclear Fission by B. Jaffe, Peter Smith Publisher Inc., 1990.
14. Nuclear Chemistry and its Applications by M. Haissinsky, Addison-Wesley, Massachusetts, 1964.
15. Applied Polymer Science by R. W. Tess and G. W. Poehlein, 2nd ed., American Chemical Society, Washington, D.C., 1985.
16. An Introduction to Polymer Science by H. G. Elias, Wiley VCH, 1997.
17. Automation in Mining, Mineral and Metal Processing 2001 by Mineral and Metal Processing Ifac Symposium on Automation in Mining, M. Araki, Pergamon Press Inc., 2001.
18. Principles of Food Chemistry by J. M. Deman, Springer-Verlag, 1999.